

REWARD SYSTEM: A MOTIVATIONAL FACTOR FOR LEARNERS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

CATRENAGEN L.SO

Southern Philippine College. Julio Pacana St., Licuan, Cagayan de Oro City

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14028334>

Published Date: 02-November-2024

Abstract: This study primarily determined the influence of Reward System to the learners' Academic Performance at East City Central School, Division of Cagayan de Oro City. It specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the learner-respondents profile enrolled for the school year 2019-2020 in terms of age, gender? 2. What is the reward system level of motivation among Grade 4 learner-respondents when grouped according to Very Highly Motivated,

Highly Motivated, Motivated, Not Motivated? Is there a significant difference between the learner-respondents profile and the reward system level of motivation in terms of age, and gender?

Keywords: Reward System, Motivational Factor, Academic Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education (DepEd) is adopting the policy guidelines on awards and recognition for the K to 12 Basic Education Program (DepEd no.36, s.2016).

The award system has been designed to formally recognize the outstanding performance and achievement of learners in academics, leadership, and social responsibility, among other aspects of student progress and development. These awards are given to encourage learners to strive for excellence and to become proactive members of school and community.

Learners receive recognition in the class based on their performance in meeting the standards of the curriculum in public elementary and secondary schools on the Basic Education Curriculum.

Teaching and learning process involves various strategies and mechanisms in order to improve students' motivation and performance. Teachers as the facilitators of learning must be skillful and knowledgeable enough to let students stay focused and well-motivated ensuring positive performance. Educational institution's performance results are dependent on students' motivation and performance. It is therefore important for the institution to find out what motivates students to learn and to performance better so that it can design a comprehensive curriculum and plan a better system to gain better results.

However, teachers must be mindful to check the effectiveness of strategy or positively contributed to the performance of the students. Before employing a strategy, teachers must have prior insights about the trend and has better perspective of the possible outcome of the process and possibly make innovations to make the venture more meaningful and relevant.

Different teaching-learning techniques and strategies are utilized by teachers in order to improve students' motivation and achieve better performance. Among the different techniques and strategies being practiced and applied in today's teachers still find the reward systems appealing to the learning process to motivate students and encourage the learners to achieve

more and perform better. In any learning set-up, reward systems have always its own way of motivating students and reinforce students' performance.

Reward system has been utilized to reinforce students' interest to learn or achieve more. Thus, a reward system makes learning more appealing and enjoyable. In the reward system as a strategy for better motivation and performance, the teacher must clearly explain to the students the purpose and the precautionary measures to consider avoiding misconceptions or distorted views towards the reward system.

To insure the quality of the learning process, constant appraisal of the strategies must be done. Effectiveness of teaching-learning strategy are commonly determined through a designed feed backing and evaluation. DepEd Order No 36 s.2016 indicates that formal recognition of student achievements that can motivate learners to strive for excellence in academic, leadership, and social responsibility must be done. However, proper implementation and utilization of the reward system is not usually guaranteed, that is why a research study is essential to address such concern.

2. THEORETICAL/CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study is based on the study of Mikander (2010) on the impact of a reward system and motivation on learners in the classroom to achieve more in academic aspect or to improve the academic performance.

Motivation is a state-of-mind, filled with energy and enthusiasm which drives a person to work in a certain way to achieve desired goals. It is a force which pushes a person to work with high level of commitment and focus even if things are against and translates into a certain kind of human behavior.

It is important to ensure that every team member in an organization is motivated. Various psychologists have studied human behavior and have formalized findings in the form various motivation theories. These motivation theories provide great understanding on how people behave and what motivates them.

Moreover, motivation is a huge field of study. There are many theories of motivation. Some of the famous motivation theories include **Maslow's hierarchy of needs**. Abraham Maslow postulated that a person will be motivated when his needs are fulfilled. The need starts from the lowest level basic needs and keeps moving up as a lower level need is fulfilled.

These are the hierarchy of needs: 1) Physiological: Physical survival necessities such as food, water, and shelter. 2) Safety: Protection from threats, deprivation, and other dangers. 3) Social (belongingness and love): The need for association, affiliation, friendship, and so on. 4) Self-esteem: The need for respect and recognition. 5) Self-actualization: The opportunity for personal development, learning, and fun/creative/challenging work. 6) Self-actualization is the highest level need to which a human being can aspire.

Studies show motivational factors (psychological, social and cultural): Intrinsic and extrinsic directions, parental influence and participation, family history, peer pressure, self-efficacy expectations, effort, value attributed to a relative, anxiety, self-regulation and determination of goals, talent perceptions, learning strategies, teaching style and school environment. The school environment optimizes motivation and learning when it is accessible, secure, positive, personalized and empowering. Teachers play a very important role in an integral part of the school environment.

Researches indicate that teachers' knowledge and skills, motivation level, qualifications, forms of evaluation, teaching style, quality of enthusiasm and enthusiasm contributed to the motivation of learners. The more enthusiastic, motivated and qualified teachers are in teaching and evaluating, the greater the capacity to increase learners' motivation to learn (Williams 2011).

Motivation is a critical component of learning and plays a very important role in helping students become involved in academic activities. Motivation is defined as a situation that gives energy to behavior, directs and sustains it. This includes goals and activity requiring that the objectives provide motivation to move and action. Action requires effort and insistence to operate for a long period of time. It involves a set of beliefs, perceptions, values, information and actions that are totally related to each other that can lead to many behaviors and understand the importance of motivation in an educational setting (Suhag,2017)

According to Schumann (2004), positive emotions (motivation) between the strong motivation and the learning process affect the cognitive process positively. The cognitive process delivers new knowledge; new knowledge learned also strengthens positive feelings (motivation). Motivation supports learning progressively so students can develop rich, adaptable skills rather than simple tasks (Beck 2004).

This is the power of learning with motivation and, in this way, students are able to acquire and think through information (Sternberg 2004). According to Suhag (2016), motivation has several effects on the learning and behavior of students: Firstly, motivation leads behavior to specific goals. Motivation sets specific goals that people strive for and, thus, influences the choices of students. Motivation also increases the effort and energy to determine whether a student will pursue a task that is difficult with enthusiasm or lifeless attitude. It is an important factor affecting the learning and success of the students by affecting the initiation and continuity of the activities, increasing the time of the students' duties.

Motivation affects how information is processed and how it is processed as it increases the cognitive processing process and motivated students get more inclined to understand and examine material than to observe learning movements.

Further, Palmer (2007), student motivation is an essential element for high quality education, and learning does not really occur unless a constant motivation is provided for the student. Internal motivation and external motivation are common types of motivation used in researches (Ryan 1985). Intrinsic motivation depends on individual feelings, internal instincts and desires, but external motivation depends on the incentives of external events, purpose, and external stimuli. Intrinsic motivation arises from within the individual, and is guided by pleasure and satisfaction performed on the challenge. Internal motivation has a unique possibility to release human potential (Deci, 2000).

This research can be regarded as very important to determine the future needs for motivation in the field of education and to provide necessary development. The purpose of this research is to determine the variables that determine the level of motivation and satisfaction.

Schema of the Study

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram showing the interplay between the dependent and independent variable of the study.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study investigates the current reward system and the motivation factor among Grade 4 section Mabini class of East City Central School, Cagayan de Oro City .

Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the learner-respondents profile enrolled for the school year 2019-2020 in terms of;
 - 1.1 age
 - 1.2 gender
2. What is the reward system level of motivation among Grade 4 learner-respondents when grouped according to;
 - 2.1 Very Highly Motivated
 - 2.2 Highly Motivated
 - 2.3 Motivated
 - 2.4 Not Motivated
3. Is there a significant difference between the learner-respondents profile and the reward system level of motivation in terms of;
 - 3.1 age
 - 3.2 gender

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research is use to determine the level of reward system employed in the classroom to the learners. In its essence, descriptive studies are use to describe various aspects of the phenomenon and to describe characteristics and/or behavior of sample population.

5. FINDINGS

The following findings are summarized as follows:

1. Majority of the respondents belonged to age bracket of **11 years old**. On the other hand, only few of the respondents are **9 years old**. The findings of this study revealed that majority of the respondent were **males**, while only almost half of the respondents were **females**. On socioeconomic status, majority of the respondents belonged to the monthly income bracket of **P2, 000 to P4, 999**, while only few are belonged to the families whose income is ranging from **P1, 999 and below**, and **P10, 000 and above**.
2. Overall, the respondents rated **strongly agree** on the reward system level of motivation among Grade 4 learner respondents. Further, the respondents rated **strongly agree** in the indicator that they are ready to increase their work efforts in order to gain the rewards. On the other hand, the respondents **strongly agreed** that the rewards are given and distributed rightfully.
3. This study found that the learner-respondents' profile in terms of age showed **negligible correlation** to the reward system level of motivation. On one hand, the learner-respondents' profile in terms of gender showed **negligible correlation** to the reward system level of motivation. Similarly, the learners' socioeconomic status showed **negligible correlation** to the reward system level of motivation as their probability value showed no significance.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, this study come up with the following conclusions:

1. It can be concluded that most pupils are 11 years old. Therefore, most learners are in the right age of their schooling as per age requirement of their grade level. Conversely, only few of the pupils are 9 years old, thus, few of them are considered school-age kids amid their grade level. In terms of gender, most pupil respondents were males, while almost only one half of the population were females. Additionally, most pupils are living with the families who have low level income or considered as poor. On one hand, only few of the parents are considered themselves as very poor and earning above minimum.

2. The respondents have full adherence to the reward system level of motivation, thus, the learners intensely agreed that reward system can be a factor to motivate them perform better in their class. Similarly, the learners have the courage to enhance their performance for the sake of rewards. However, the learners are quite challenged in terms of equitable distribution of the external rewards.

3. The researcher concluded that the profile of the pupils in terms of age and the implementation of reward system level of motivation were all found not to be significant, thus, they are not correlated. Therefore, the age of the learners does not have significant relationship to the reward system level of motivation. Henceforth, the learners' gender does not significantly associate with their level of motivation. Moreover, the financial status of the pupils' family and the reward system level of motivation were all found not to be significant, thus, they were not correlated. Thus, socioeconomic status does not have significant association with the implementation of the reward system level of motivation. Therefore, the learners are still motivated to study regardless of the socioeconomic status of their families.

REFERENCES

- [1] Armstrong, M. 2001, *A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practices*, London: Kogan Page Ltd.
- [2] Armstrong, M. 2003, *A Handbook on Human Resource Management*, London: Kogan.
- [3] Armstrong, Michael & Brown, Duncan. 2006, *Strategic Reward*, 1st edition. Great Britan: Kogan Page Limited, 266 p.
- [4] Arnold, J., Robertson, I. T. and Cooper, C. L. 1991, *Work Psychology*, London: Pitman.
- [5] Herzberg, F. W., Mauser, B. and Snyderman, B. 1957, *The Motivation to Work*, New York: Wiley.
- [6] Luthans, F. 1998, *Organisational Behaviour*. 8th ed. Boston: Irwin McGraw-Hill.
- [7] Maslow, Abraham H. 1954, *Motivation and Personality*, 2nd edition. Harper & Row, 369 p.
- [8] Miner, J. B., Ebrahimi, B. and Wachtel, J.M. (1995). How deficiency in management contributes to the United States' competitiveness problem and what can be done about it? *Human Resource Management Journal*, Fall, Pp. 363.
- [9] Pitts, Collins. 1995, *Motivating Your Organization*, 1st edition. McGraw-Hill International, 187 p.
- [10] Zingheim, Patricia K & Schuster, Jay R. 2000, *Pay People Right*, 1st edition. California: Jossey-Bass Inc, 388 p. <http://www.dailyteachingtools.com/cooperative-learning-evaluate.html#2>